

Torsional characteristics of carbon nanotubes: micropolar elasticity models and molecular dynamics simulation

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Abstract: Efficient application of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in nano-devices and nano-materials requires comprehensive understanding of their mechanical properties. As observations suggest size dependent behaviour, non-classical theories preserving the memory of body's internal structure via additional material parameters offer great potential when a continuum modelling is to be preferred. In the present study, micropolar theory of elasticity is adopted due to its peculiar character allowing for incorporation of scale effects through additional kinematic descriptors and work-conjugated stress measures. An optimisation approach is presented to provide unified material parameters for two specific class of single-walled carbon nanotubes (e.g. armchair and zigzag) by minimizing the difference between the apparent shear modulus obtained from molecular dynamics (MD) simulation and micropolar beam model considering both solid and tubular cross-sections. The results clearly reveal that micropolar theory is more suitable compared to internally constraint couple stress theory, due to the essentiality of having skew-symmetric stress and strain measures, as well as to the classical local theory (Cauchy of Grade 1), which cannot accounts for scale effects. To the best of authors' knowledge, this is the first time that unified material parameters of CNTs are derived through a combined MD-micropolar continuum theory.

Keywords: Micropolar continua; Molecular Dynamics; SWCNTs parameters identification; Optimisation

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1. Introduction

Discovered by Iijima [1,2], carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have received great attention due to their superior mechanical, optical, thermal and electrical properties [3–7]. Their exhaustive application in nanoscopic field as springs [8], oscillators [9,10], actuators [11,12], transistors [12], sensors [13] and reinforcement element [14–17], requires a complete understanding of the underlying mechanical properties. In doing so, two main approaches, namely discrete and multiscale continuum models are favored depending on the specificity of the problem, while experiments are not preferred due to the design complexity and expenses in nano-scale.

In discrete modelling technique, atoms and interatomic bonds are explicitly modelled using first-principle or semi-empirical methods (e.g. tight binding, ab initio models, molecular dynamics (MD) simulation) [18–20]. Despite their capability of representing the actual behaviour of the media, discrete modelling techniques are not very practical due to their computational expense, which rapidly increase with total number of degree of freedoms [21]. Classical theory of elasticity (Cauchy of Grade 1), on the other hand, fails to accurately homogenize the discrete nature into a continuum medium for a structure having comparable internal and external lengths [22,23]. This drawback can

35 be overcome by means of non-classical (non-local) continuum theories which simulta-
36 neously utilize field description at coarse level, and preserve the memory of material's
37 underlying structure at fine level through internal scale parameters [24–29] that can refer
38 to different physical features ranging from nano order (e.g. distance between atoms in a
39 nanoscopic structure) up to meso/macro orders (size of particle/grain in a composite
40 medium) as demonstrated in different studies [30–33].

41 Incorporation of non-locality related parameters to the continuum theory might
42 be obtained through additional kinematic descriptors (non-standard primal fields) and
43 work-conjugated stress measures (non-standard dual fields) as in 'implicit/weak' non-
44 local models (multi-field continua) or through constitutive equations containing integral,
45 integro-differential or finite-difference operators of spatial fields as in 'explicit/strong'
46 non-local models [22,29,34,35]. Although the majority of literature, that deals with con-
47 tinuum modelling of CNTs [36–41], employs explicitly non-local Eringen's theory of
48 elasticity, as it perfectly captures the long-range interaction between atoms by relating
49 stress at a point to the strain of entire domain through an attenuation-type kernel function
50 [42], few works are devoted to the application of implicitly non-local microcontinuum
51 field theories. For instance, Xie and Long [43] adopted micropolar theory to calculate
52 the fundamental frequencies of single-walled CNTs (SWCNTs) and double-walled CNTs
53 (DWCNTs), while others applied couple stress continuum theory (i.e. a subcase of
54 micropolar theory with an internal constraint; micro-rotations equal the macro-rotation
55 [44–46])[47–49]. Akgöz and Civalek [47] calculated the critical axial compressive buck-
56 ling loads of CNTs using the Euler-Bernoulli beam model based on the modified couple
57 stress theory, and presented the influence of length scale parameter on the buckling
58 characteristics. Khajueenejad and Ghanbari [48] studied axial buckling of CNTs using
59 Timoshenko beam model and modified couple stress theory. By correlating the derived
60 buckling loads with the MD simulations data of Liew et al. [50], they estimated the
61 variable couple stress internal length parameter for zigzag and armchair nanotubes. Ak-
62 barzadeh and Soltani [49] added another length scale parameter to the modified couple
63 stress theory to match the theoretical relation for longitudinal and flexural dispersion of
64 CNTs to the data provided by Wang et al. [51].

65 In the light of these informations, micropolar continuum theory is deemed as a good
66 candidate to model size dependent mechanical behaviour of CNTs as underlying hexag-
67 onal lattice structure is consistent to the essence/existence of micro-rotations, hence
68 encourages utilization of theories endowed with additional kinematic descriptors [29,52–
69 54]. To determine corresponding material parameters, a wide range of armchair and
70 zigzag nanotubes are examined by both discrete and continuum modelling techniques.
71 In doing so, primarily, MD simulations of nanotubes having different diameters but same
72 aspect ratio are performed to show the occurrence of size effects through interpreting the
73 torsional data (i.e. torsional rigidity) [55,56]. Since herein the focus is on torsional rigidi-
74 ties, which is shown to be independent of the aspect ratio of corresponding nanotube
75 [38], moderately short nanotubes are studied for computational efficiency. Note that
76 different states of loading exhibiting size effects (e.g. bending) are possible. Although all
77 would yield same material parameters, imposing the end conditions for torsional loading
78 in MD simulations is much more straightforward and accurate compared to other types
79 of loading. For continuum modelling, CNTs are considered as micropolar beams whose
80 cross-sectional area remain planar after deformation (i.e. no warping), and according
81 closed-form expressions of apparent shear modulus are re-derived considering both
82 solid and hollow cross-sections. Even though CNTs genuinely are hollow cylinders,
83 solid cross-section case can be an expedient while dealing with continuum modelling
84 of nanotubes employed as reinforcement elements [57–60]. Finally, a unified parameter
85 set, as well as thickness, of equivalent continuum model is derived for each class of
86 SWCNTs chirality by comparing the corresponding data obtained from discrete MD and
87 continuum models (micropolar, couple stress and classical) by virtue of a non-linear
88 optimisation approach. To highlight the importance of having skew-symmetric stress

89 and strain measures as in micropolar theory, optimisation process is re-performed by
 90 defining an internal constraint on micro-rotations leading to symmetric couple stress
 91 theory. To the best of authors' knowledge this is the first time that a combined MD-
 92 micropolar continuum theory is employed to model the size-dependent mechanical
 93 behaviour of CNTs.

94 The rest of the paper is organised as follows; Section 2 describes the details on
 95 MD simulation and presents the primary obtained results. In Section 3, the governing
 96 equations and the derivation of relations of micropolar torsional rigidities are presented.
 97 In Section 4, the non-local material parameters are determined comparing the results
 98 of MD simulation and continuum model through a non-linear optimisation approach.
 99 Finally, the concluding remarks are presented in Section 5.

100 2. Discrete model

101 Single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) can be described as a single layer of
 102 graphene sheet that has been rolled into a seamless hollow cylinder with a constant
 103 radius. They have a mean diameter, d_0 , a total length, L (see Fig. 1), and further
 104 categorised as armchair ($m = n$), zigzag ($n = 0$) and chiral ($m \neq n$) according to the
 105 direction of wrapping:

$$\mathbf{C}_h = m\mathbf{a}_1 + n\mathbf{a}_2 = (m, n) \quad (1)$$

106 where \mathbf{C}_h refers to chiral vector, and is specified by chiral index (m, n) , alongside
 107 with basis vectors of graphene lattice \mathbf{a}_1 and \mathbf{a}_2 [61–64]. For the sake of computational
 108 cost, the analyses herein are performed considering eight armchair and eight zigzag
 109 nanotubes having different mean diameters $d_0 = 6.3 - 16.3 \text{ \AA}$ ($1 \text{ \AA} = 10^{-10} \text{ m}$), while
 110 overall lengths are selected to result in moderately short nanotubes; $L \approx 5.0 d_0$, since
 111 torsional stiffness is proven to be independent of the aspect ratio through MD simulations
 112 performed for (5,5) nanotubes having different lengths, as also reported in the literature
 113 [38,65]. The discrete models are built using Visual Molecular Dynamics (VMD) software
 114 developed by University of Illinois [66], and corresponding MD simulations are carried
 115 out by employing the open source Large-scale Atomic/Molecular Massively Parallel
 116 Simulator (LAMMPS) package, that is widely used for ensembles of solid, liquid or
 117 gaseous particles [67].

118 MD simulation has been introduced by Alder and Wainwright [68,69], as a com-
 119 putational method that allows one to predict the time evolution of atomic/molecular
 120 systems, based on classical Newtonian mechanics, and generally admitted as *numerical*
 121 or *computer* experiments. In MD, atoms are assumed as interacting solid spheres, the po-
 122 sition, \mathbf{r} , velocity, \mathbf{v} , and acceleration, \mathbf{a} , of each atom are to be determined for each time
 123 step, t , via solving corresponding differential equations system, by virtue of integration
 124 algorithms [70]:

$$\mathbf{F}_i = -\nabla_{\mathbf{r}_i} U(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) = m_i \frac{d^2 \mathbf{r}_i(t)}{dt^2} \quad (2)$$

125 where \mathbf{F} refers to the force vector acting on the i -th atom, and can be written as the
 126 gradient of the total potential energy function, U , of a system consisting of N atoms. In
 127 the most general case, energy function includes one-body, U_1 , (describes external force
 128 fields or boundary conditions), two-body, U_2 , (depends on the distance between pairs
 129 of atoms) and three-body (or higher-order), U_3 , (based on the geometry of the atomic
 130 arrangement) potentials:

$$U(\mathbf{r}_1, \dots, \mathbf{r}_N) = \sum_i U_1(\mathbf{r}_i) + \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} U_2(\mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_j) + \sum_i \sum_{j \neq i} \sum_{k \neq i, j} U_3(\mathbf{r}_i, \mathbf{r}_j, \mathbf{r}_k) + \dots \quad (3)$$

131 In the present study, simulations are performed in a canonical (NVT) ensemble
 132 where the total number of atoms, volume of the simulation box, and the temperature

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of SWCNT and its equivalent continuum model boundary conditions for torsional loading

133 of the system are kept constant [67]. The velocity-Verlet integrator algorithm is used
 134 with a time step of 1 fs (1 femtosecond = 1×10^{-15} sec), and the interatomic relation
 135 between carbon atoms is described using adaptive intermolecular reactive empirical
 136 bond order (AIREBO) potential with a cut-off radius of 10.2 Å [71]. The temperature
 137 is kept constant at 10 Kelvin (K) to reduce noise and thermal effect with the aid of
 138 Nose-Hoover thermostat, while before the thermalisation, an energy minimization is
 139 conducted by using the conjugate gradient algorithm in order to remove the primitive
 140 forces above 1×10^{-12} eV/Å. After thermalisation, clamped-free nanotubes are subjected
 141 to torsional loading by a sequential rotation and relaxation route, called as displacement-
 142 rate controlled simulation. To apply the corresponding boundary conditions, movement
 143 of atoms located at the right end are restricted in all directions, while axially fixed atoms
 144 at the left end are twisted along z-axis with an incremental twist angle of 0.006 radians
 145 (see Fig. 1). After each rotation, the remaining atoms (those that are not fixed) are
 146 subjected to NVT ensemble for 20000 time steps (20 picosecond = 20×10^{-12} sec) to let
 147 the structure attain the minimum energy state at each increment, which corresponds to
 148 a twist angle speed of 0.0003 rad/ps, and ensures quasi-static state. The span of fixed
 149 atoms at each end, l_{fixed} , is arranged to be in accordance with the overall length of the
 150 nanotube, such that the ratio in-between remains constant (i.e. $l_{\text{fixed}}/L \approx 25\%$).

Table 1. Parameters of carbon nanotubes (measured after energy minimization and thermal equilibrium steps) and corresponding results obtained from MD simulations.

	chirality (m,n)	diameter d_0 (Å)	length L (Å)	torsional stiffness K (nN.nm)	critical angle θ_{crt} (rad)
armchair	(5,5)	6.78	32.80	10.801	0.726
	(6,6)	8.09	40.06	14.877	0.600
	(7,7)	9.42	47.29	19.576	0.528
	(8,8)	10.74	54.56	24.863	0.468
	(9,9)	12.07	61.80	30.785	0.420
	(10,10)	13.40	66.61	38.678	0.396
	(11,11)	14.73	73.87	45.845	0.372
	(12,12)	16.06	81.12	53.613	0.354
zigzag	(8,0)	6.33	30.62	9.511	0.798
	(10,0)	7.84	39.03	13.662	0.654
	(12,0)	9.36	47.44	18.602	0.546
	(14,0)	10.89	53.02	25.716	0.432
	(16,0)	12.42	61.40	32.304	0.384
	(18,0)	13.95	68.38	40.312	0.336
	(20,0)	15.48	78.19	47.621	0.300
(21,0)	16.25	82.38	51.759	0.288	

During simulation, the total potential energy, U , torsional moment, T , and twist angle at the tip, θ , are recorded at the end of each increment (i.e. every 20 ps) by averaging the last twenty data. Corresponding torsional stiffness, K , which is derived as follows, are tabulated in Table 1 alongside with critical buckling angles, θ_{crt} ,

$$K = \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial \theta^2} \quad (4)$$

151 As reported by Gauthier and Jahsmán [55], the apparent shear modulus, ($\Omega G =$
 152 KL/I_p), in torsional loading of a cylindrical specimen with micropolar non-local char-
 153 acter increases with decreasing diameter. This is in contradiction to the local case for
 154 which no size variation is expected; indeed, the apparent shear modulus, J/I_p , turns out
 155 to be a constant, G , and independent of the diameter of the specimen (Fig. (2)). To check
 156 if the non-local behaviour is verified for nanotubes considered herein, the variation of
 157 apparent shear modulus, which is calculated using the torsional stiffness values obtained
 158 from MD simulations, with respect to diameters is plotted at Fig. (2), as a preliminary
 159 investigation. Even though the thickness of nanotubes is not known yet, polar moment
 160 of inertia can be obtained by assuming the case of solid cross section; $I_p = (\pi d_0^4)/32$. The
 161 trend of curve evidently verifies the non-local behaviour since apparent shear modulus
 162 depends on the diameter as opposed to what is observed in local case.

Figure 2. Variation of apparent shear modulus with respect to mean diameter for armchair and zigzag CNTs, considering solid cross section

163 The reaction forces emerged at each end are documented to assure that no significant
 164 axial force, which might spoil the pure torsion character of loading, is generated. By
 165 increasing the relaxation time from 5000 to 60000 fs (i.e. 5000, 10000, 20000, 60000 fs)
 166 while keeping incremental twist angle fixed to 0.006 rad, the effect of twist rate is studied
 167 through comparing torsional rigidity of carbon nanotubes having a chirality of (12,12),
 168 which requires the longest relaxation time to find the equilibrium position of atoms
 169 among the models considered herein.

170 For validation of MD simulations, torsional rigidity ($J = KL = T_{crt}L/\theta_{crt}$), which is
 171 considered as the main measured quantity in torsional testing, the data of clamped-free
 172 armchair and zigzag nanotubes with (10,10) and (16,0) chirality are compared with those
 173 of Chowdhury [65]. Corresponding relative difference between the results, which are
 174 1.28%, 2.03% respectively, proves the accuracy of the simulations, and the independence
 175 of the torsional stiffness from the total length of the nanotube.

176 3. Equivalent continuum models

177 In the present section, the governing equations for the pure torsion of a circular cylinder
 178 made of homogeneous isotropic micropolar elastic material is presented. Then, the steps
 179 to the derivation of micropolar torsional rigidities are outlined. All the equations are
 180 performed within the linearised kinematic framework. CNT is modelled as a micropolar
 181 continuum beam, with considering both cases of solid and hollow cross sections.

182 3.1. Micropolar hollow circular cylinder

183 In this section, the solution strategy is based on Taliercio's study on the micropolar
 184 hollow cylinder under twist [72]. Fig. 1 shows the equivalent circular cylinder of length
 185 L in a cylindrical coordinate system (r, θ, z) with z aligned with cylinder axis. R_o and R_i
 186 denote the outer and inner radii, respectively.

187 While fixing one end of the cylinder ($z = 0$), the other end ($z = L$) is subjected
 188 to a rotation $\theta_t L$ about the cylinder axis leading to the following displacement and
 189 microrotation fields:

$$u_r = 0, \quad u_\theta = \theta_t r z, \quad u_z = 0, \quad \phi_r = \theta_t \Phi(r), \quad \phi_\theta = 0, \quad \phi_z = \theta_t z \quad (5)$$

190 where θ_t is the unit angle of twist, and u_i and ϕ_i ($i = r, \theta, z$) denote the displacement
 191 and microrotation components, respectively. In Eq. (5), $\Phi(r)$ is an unknown material
 192 and geometrical function with length dimension, which denotes the coupling between
 193 micro-rotations in axial and radial directions. The validation of the assumption in Eq.
 194 (5) is guaranteed as the final solution which fulfills all the equations will be found.
 195 According to Kirchhoff's theorem in linear elasticity this must be the exact solution. In
 196 accordance with displacement and microrotation fields given in Eq. (5), no warping
 197 occurs during deformation and the cross section remains planar.

198 In a micropolar body, both the position and orientation are used to describe the
 199 material particles [26,28,52,73]. Under these assumptions the kinematic compatibility
 200 equations are:

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = u_{j,i} + e_{ijk} \phi_{k,r}, \quad \chi_{ij} = \phi_{j,i} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 3) \quad (6)$$

201 where ε_{ij} and χ_{ij} denote the components of micropolar strain and curvature tensors
 202 and e_{ijk} is the third order permutation tensor. Substituting Eq.(5) into Eq.(6), the only
 203 non-zero components become:

$$\varepsilon_{\theta z} = -\theta_t \Phi(r), \quad \varepsilon_{z\theta} = \theta_t (r + \Phi(r)), \quad \chi_{rr} = \theta_t \Phi'(r), \quad \chi_{\theta\theta} = \theta_t \frac{\Phi(r)}{r}, \quad \chi_{zz} = \theta_t \quad (7)$$

204 where the prime denotes derivative with respect to r .

205 The constitutive equations for a linear isotropic micropolar material read:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \lambda \varepsilon_{kk} \delta_{ij} + \mu \varepsilon_{ji} + (\mu + \kappa) \varepsilon_{ij}, \quad \mu_{ij} = \alpha \chi_{kk} \delta_{ij} + \beta \chi_{ji} + \gamma \chi_{ij} \quad (8)$$

206 Eq.(8) contains six elastic material constants; the two Lamé's constants, λ , and μ
 207 and four additional parameters, α , β , γ and κ emerging from micropolar theory [56]. The
 208 following so-called engineering constants are also derived based on the aforementioned
 209 six parameters providing better physical insight [56]:

- 210 • $G = \mu + \kappa/2$: shear modulus
- 211 • $N = \sqrt{\kappa/(2(\mu + \kappa))}$: coupling number
- 212 • $l_t = \sqrt{(\beta + \gamma)/(2\mu + \kappa)}$: characteristic length for torsion
- 213 • $\psi = (\beta + \gamma)/(\alpha + \beta + \gamma)$: polar ratio
- 214 • $E = (2\mu + \kappa)(3\lambda + 2\mu + \kappa)/(2\lambda + 2\mu + \kappa)$: Young's modulus
- 215 • $\nu = \lambda/(2\lambda + 2\mu + \kappa)$: Poisson's ratio
- 216 • $l_b = \sqrt{\gamma/2(2\mu + \kappa)}$: characteristic length for bending

217 Substituting the strains and curvatures in Eq.(6) into the constitutive law (Eq.(8))
218 leads to the following stress and couple-stresses relations:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_{\theta z} &= (\mu r - \kappa \Phi(r))\theta_t & \sigma_{z\theta} &= ((\mu + \kappa)r + \kappa \Phi(r))\theta_t \\
 \mu_{rr} &= [(\alpha + \beta + \gamma)\Phi'(r) + \alpha\left(\frac{\Phi(r)}{r} + 1\right)]\theta_t \\
 \mu_{zz} &= [(\alpha + \beta + \gamma) + \alpha\left(\Phi'(r) + \frac{\Phi(r)}{r}\right)]\theta_t \\
 \mu_{\theta\theta} &= [(\alpha + \beta + \gamma)\frac{\Phi(r)}{r} + \alpha(\Phi'(r) + 1)]\theta_t
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

219 In the absence of body force and body couples, the equilibrium equations can be
220 derived in the form:

$$\sigma_{ji,j} = 0, \quad \mu_{jk,j} - e_{ijk}\sigma_{ji} = 0 \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 3) \tag{10}$$

221 As the non-vanishing non-symmetric stress and couple stress measures expressed
222 in Eq. (9) are independent of θ and z , only the following relation corresponding to
223 angular equilibrium equation in radial direction remains:

$$\frac{\partial \mu_{rr}}{\partial r} + \frac{\mu_{rr}}{r} + \sigma_{\theta z} - \sigma_{z\theta} - \frac{\mu_{\theta\theta}}{r} = 0 \tag{11}$$

224 It results in the following differential equation for $\Phi(r)$:

$$r^2\Phi''(r) + r\Phi'(r) - (1 + p^2r^2)\Phi(r) - \frac{p^2}{2}r^3 = 0 \tag{12}$$

225 which has the solution:

$$\Phi(r) = AI_1(pr) + BK_1(pr) - r/2 \tag{13}$$

226 where $p^2 = 2k/(\alpha + \beta + \gamma)$ and I_n and K_n are the modified Bessel functions of the
227 first and second kind of order n .

228 From balance considerations, the following relations hold as the boundary condi-
229 tions:

$$t_i = \sigma_{ji}n_j, \quad \mu_i = \mu_{ji}n_j \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 3) \tag{14}$$

230 where t_i and μ_i are the components of surface traction and surface couple traction,
231 respectively and n_j is the unit outward normal vector of the continuum boundary. The
232 coefficient A and B are determined by applying traction free boundary conditions on the
233 lateral surfaces ($r = R_i$ and $r = R_o$):

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= \frac{2R_oR_i s \kappa (K_0(pR_i) - K_0(pR_o) - s^2(R_iK_1(pR_o) - R_oK_1(pR_i)))}{\Delta} \\
 B &= \frac{2R_oR_i s \kappa (I_0(pR_i) - I_0(pR_o) + s^2(R_iK_1(pR_o) - R_oI_1(pR_i)))}{\Delta}
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

234 with $s = p(\beta + \gamma)$ and

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta &= 2(2R_o\kappa I_0(pR_o) - sI_1(pR_o))(2R_i\kappa K_0(pR_i) + sK_1(pR_i)) \\
 &\quad - 2(2R_i\kappa I_0(pR_i) - sI_1(pR_i))(2R_o\kappa K_0(pR_o) + sK_1(pR_o))
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

235 The torsional rigidity of the micropolar cylinder, J_m , is defined as the ratio of the
236 applied twisting torque (T) on any cross section (C) to the unit angle of twist:

$$J_m = \frac{T}{\theta_t} = \frac{\int_C (\sigma_{z\theta} r + \mu_{zz}) dC}{\theta_t} \quad (17)$$

237 In Eq. (17), $\sigma_{z\theta}$ and μ_{zz} can be found by substituting $\Phi(r)$ from Eq. (13) into the
238 related expressions in Eq. (9) as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{z\theta} &= ((\mu + \kappa)r + \kappa(AI_1(pr) + BK_1(pr) - r/2))\theta_t = (Gr + \kappa f_1)\theta_t \\ \mu_{zz} &= [(\alpha + \beta + \gamma) + \alpha(A(pI_0 - \frac{I_1}{r}) + B(-pK_0 - \frac{K_1}{r}) - \frac{1}{2} + \dots \\ &\quad \frac{1}{r}(AI_1(pr) + BK_1(pr)))]\theta_t \\ &= [(\beta + \gamma) + \alpha p f_0]\theta_t \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

239 where

$$\begin{aligned} f_0 &= AI_0(pr) - BK_0(pr) \\ f_1 &= AI_1(pr) + BK_1(pr) \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

240 Using integral relations for modified Bessel functions [74] and integrating over the
241 cross section (C), one can obtain :

$$\begin{aligned} J_m &= G(\pi \frac{R_o^4 - R_i^4}{2}) + (\beta + \gamma)(\pi(R_o^2 - R_i^2)) + \dots \\ &\quad 2\pi \left[\frac{A}{p}(p\alpha(rI_1(pr)) + \kappa r^2 I_2(pr)) + \dots \right. \\ &\quad \left. B(\alpha(rK_1(pr)) - \frac{\kappa r^2}{p} K_2(pr)) \right]_{R_i}^{R_o} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

242 A more useful quantity to define is the nondimensional rigidity ratio for hollow
243 cylinders Ω_h , which is the ratio of micropolar torsional rigidity to the classical counter-
244 part:

$$\Omega_h = \frac{J_m}{J_{ch}} = 1 + \frac{(2I_t)^2}{R_o^2 - R_i^2} + \frac{4A(p\alpha\eta_1^I + \kappa\eta_2^I) + 4B(p\alpha\eta_1^{II} - \kappa\eta_2^{II})}{pG(R_o^4 - R_i^4)} \quad (21)$$

245 where $J_{ch} = G(\pi \frac{R_o^4 - R_i^4}{2})$ is the well-known classical torsional rigidity for hollow
246 cylinders, where $\eta_n^I = R_o^n I_n(pR_o) - R_i^n I_n(pR_i)$ and $\eta_n^{II} = R_o^n K_n(pR_o) - R_i^n K_n(pR_i)$,
247 $n = 1, 2$.

It should be noted that, although, the solution method in this section is mainly based on [72], the final formulation is different and more convenient to adopt. A new parameter η_2^{II} is defined, instead of the parameter named ξ in [72], avoiding the uneasy calculation of generalized Meijer G function, G_{pq}^{mn} , in ξ evaluation;

$$\xi = R_o^3 G_{13}^{21} \left(\frac{pR_o}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \left| \frac{-1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{-3}{2} \right. \right) - R_i^3 G_{13}^{21} \left(\frac{pR_i}{2}, \frac{1}{2} \left| \frac{-1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{-3}{2} \right. \right) \quad (22)$$

248 3.2. Micropolar solid circular cylinder

249 In an early study conducted by Gauthier and Jahsmann [55], the following relation is
250 proposed for the torsional rigidity ratio of a micropolar solid cylinder of radius R :

$$\Omega_s = \frac{J_m}{J_{cs}} = 1 + 6 \left(\frac{I_t}{R} \right)^2 \frac{1 - \frac{4}{3}\psi X}{1 - \psi X} \quad (23)$$

Figure 3. Plot of torsional rigidity divided by the square of the diameter vs. the square of the external diameter to characterize Cosserat parameters

251 where $X = (I_1(pR)/pRI_0(pR))$ and $J_{cs} = G(\pi \frac{R^4}{2})$ denotes the classical torsional
 252 rigidity for solid cylinders.

253 An alternative expression can be easily obtained by considering $R_i = 0$, in the case
 254 of hollow cylinder introduced in the previous section. In order to avoid singularity at
 255 the origin, the boundary conditions change to $\Phi(0) = 0$ and $\mu_{rr}(R_o) = 0$, leading to the
 256 following coefficient constants [72]:

$$A = \frac{Rs}{2(2R\kappa I_0(pR) - sI_1(pR))}, \quad B = 0 \quad (24)$$

257 The obtained rigidity ratio through the two equations (Eqs. (24) and (23)) can be
 258 proved to be equal.

259 Based on the relation in Eq. (23), Lake [56] proposed to plot torsional rigidity
 260 divided by the square of the diameter vs. the square of the diameter to characterize
 261 Cosserat parameters; the slope of the asymptotic straight line is proportional to the shear
 262 modulus, G , and the characteristic lengths, l_t , can be extracted from the intercept of
 263 the extrapolated straight portion of the curve upon the ordinate. The coupling number
 264 N and polar ratio ψ also affect the plot shape, especially at the vicinity of the origin,
 265 however, they cannot be precisely determined solely using the plot.

266 Finally, it should be noted that according to both Eqs. (21) and (23), for micropolar
 267 bodies, Ω_h and $\Omega_s \geq 1$. This means that the torsional rigidity is higher than expected
 268 classically. This reveals the occurrence of "size effect" [56] which is more dominant in
 269 smaller diameters, where the internal length becomes comparable to cylinder diameter.

270 In addition, let us name the product $\Omega_h G$ or $\Omega_s G$ as the apparent shear moduli as
 271 suggested by [55]. This definition is expedient as in a pure torsion experiment, it can be
 272 easily calculated through torque-twist measurements:

$$\Omega_h G = \frac{T}{\theta_t \pi (R_o^4 - R_i^4) / 2} \quad \text{or,} \quad \Omega_s G = \frac{T}{\theta_t \pi (R^4) / 2} \quad (25)$$

273 It should be noted that if Ω_h or Ω_s are equal to unity, the classical Cauchy relation
 274 for shear modulus is recovered as follows;

$$G = \frac{T}{\theta_t \pi (R_o^4 - R_i^4) / 2} \quad \text{or,} \quad G = \frac{T}{\theta_t \pi (R^4) / 2} \quad (26)$$

275 Finally, considering the mean diameter, d_0 , and then substituting into Eqs. (21) and
276 (23), the expressions for apparent shear moduli can be written as follow:

$$\begin{aligned}\Omega_h G &= G \left(1 + \frac{(4l_t)^2}{(d_0 + h)^2 - (d_0 - h)^2} \right) + \frac{64A(p\alpha\eta_1^I + \kappa\eta_2^I) + 64B(p\alpha\eta_1^{II} - \kappa\eta_2^{II})}{p((d_0 + h)^4 - (d_0 - h)^4)} \\ \Omega_s G &= G \left(1 + 6 \left(\frac{2l_t}{d_0} \right)^2 \frac{1 - \frac{4}{3}\psi X}{1 - \psi X} \right)\end{aligned}\quad (27)$$

277 These equations are expressed in terms of micropolar parameters and, in the case
278 of hollow cylinders, also in terms of thickness, h .

279 3.3. Couple stress theory

280 For homogenization of discrete structures possessing strong anisotropy as orthotropic
281 textures, a full micropolar model is needed (for more discussion on the topic see [31,
282 54,75]). In this case, the non-symmetries (skew-symmetries) of the strain and stress
283 tensors play a relevant role. However, if the material texture exhibits special groups of
284 symmetries, as orthotetragonal textures, the non-symmetries of the stresses and strains
285 disappear. In this case, the couple stress theory may be considered as a good candidate
286 (in a different framework see for instance [76]). For a chiral CNT in general, the non-
287 symmetries of strain and stress in the axial and circumferential directions are quite
288 predictable, therefore, a full micropolar model is to be preferred for the homogenization
289 process. However, the symmetrical structure of armchair and zigzag CNTs, triggers the
290 possibility of the application of couple stress model with lower number of unknown
291 material parameters to be characterized. This will also be examined in the present paper.

292 In couple stress theory, the micro-rotations are constrained to follow the local rigid
293 rotation:

$$\phi_i = -\frac{1}{2}\epsilon_{ijk}u_{j,k}\quad (28)$$

294 that leads to the classical compatibility equation;

$$\epsilon_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i})\quad (29)$$

295 Herein, couple stress theory is attained by imposing the symmetries on the strain
296 tensor, hence, according to Eq. (7), the only non-zero strain terms in the pure torsion
297 problem are found to be $\epsilon_{\theta z}$ and $\epsilon_{z\theta}$, and their equivalency results in:

$$\Phi(r) = -\frac{r}{2}\quad (30)$$

298 By substituting Eq. (30) into Eq. (9), one can obtain the following relations for the
299 stresses and couple-stresses;

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{z\theta} &= \sigma_{\theta z} = \left(\mu + \frac{\kappa}{2}\right)r\theta_t = Gr\theta_t \\ \mu_{zz} &= (\beta + \gamma)\theta_t = 2Gl_t^2\theta_t \\ \mu_{\theta\theta} &= \mu_{rr} = -\frac{(\beta + \gamma)}{2}\theta_t = -Gl_t^2\theta_t\end{aligned}\quad (31)$$

300 Note that the obtained strains, rotations, stresses and couple stresses are quite
301 consistent with the torsion problem of a circular cylinder, proposed by Yang et al. [77]
302 in the development of a modified couple stress theory, except that in their study the
303 relations are presented in terms of deviatoric part of the couple stress tensor, m_{ij} , while
304 in the present problem $\mu_{ij} = m_{ij}$, as $\mu_{ii} = 0$.

305 Finally, division of the applied torque to the unit angle of twist gives the torsional
306 rigidity for the couple stress model, J_{co} :

$$\begin{aligned} J_{co} &= \frac{T}{\theta_t} = \frac{\int_C (\sigma_{z\theta} r + \mu_{zz}) dC}{\theta_t} = \int_C (Gr(r) + 2Gl_t^2) dC \\ &= G(\pi \frac{R_o^4 - R_i^4}{2}) + G\pi 2l_t^2 (R_o^2 - R_i^2) \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

307 with the corresponding rigidity ratio, Ω_{hco} :

$$\Omega_{hco} = \frac{J_{co}}{J_{ch}} = 1 + \frac{(2l_t)^2}{R_o^2 + R_i^2} \quad (33)$$

308 By applying the same procedure in the case of solid cylinder, the following relation
309 for the rigidity ratio is obtained, which coincides with the one proposed in [77]:

$$\Omega_{sco} = \frac{J_{co}}{J_{cs}} = 1 + 6\left(\frac{l_t}{R}\right)^2 \quad (34)$$

310 4. Identification of material parameters and discussion

311 To consider CNT as an equivalent micropolar or couple-stress non-local continuum
312 model, one needs to know the corresponding non-local parameters as well as the nan-
313 otube thickness. In the present section, the torsional rigidities obtained from MD simula-
314 tions in Section 2 and the continuum relations presented in Section 3 are incorporated
315 through an optimisation approach to determine the non-local parameters and the tube
316 thickness. The results obtained for the three continuum models, namely; micropolar,
317 couple stress and classical Cauchy models for predicting the torsional rigidity of CNT
318 are compared with each other, and with the results of MD simulations considered as
319 benchmark solution.

320 For the optimisation approach we search for

$$\min\{F_{obj}(G, N, \psi, l_t, h)\} \quad (35)$$

321 utilizing a non-linear least square method. F_{obj} is a non-linear function which is the
322 Euclidean norm of the difference between the torsional rigidity, " J ", directly obtained
323 from the MD simulations and the ones predicted by micropolar model. As explained in
324 Section 3, J/I_p is equal to the apparent shear modulus, ΩG , in the continuum model;

$$F_{obj} = \left| \frac{\frac{J_{MD}}{I_p} - (\Omega G)_{Continuum}}{\frac{J_{MD}}{I_p}} \right| \quad (36)$$

325 For the micropolar case, the five unknown parameters are G , N , ψ , l_t and the
326 wall thickness, h (Eq. (35)). Using the principle of non-negative energy, the first four
327 unknowns are under the following inequality constraints [55,72]:

$$0 \leq G, \quad 0 \leq N \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq \psi \leq 1.5, \quad 0 \leq l_t \quad (37)$$

328 Another inequality constraint is applied on the thickness based on the Vodenitcharova
329 and Zhang criterion [78];

$$0 < h \leq 1.42 \quad (38)$$

330 The unknowns reduce to G , l_t and h for the case of couple stress theory.

331 Note that, alternatively, the unknown variables could be considered as κ , α , $\beta + \gamma$,
332 μ and h , with the following constraints instead of Eq. (37) [73]:

$$0 \leq 2\mu + \kappa, \quad 0 \leq \kappa, \quad 0 \leq 3\alpha + \beta + \gamma \quad 0 \leq \beta + \gamma \quad (39)$$

333 However, once the four engineering non-local parameters are determined, the
334 alternative non-local ones can be derived through the following relations;

$$\kappa = \frac{2GN^2}{1-N^2}, \quad \alpha = \frac{2Gl_t^2}{\psi(1-\psi)}, \quad \beta + \gamma = 2Gl_t^2, \quad \mu = \frac{2G-k}{2} \quad (40)$$

335 It should be noted that an optimisation problem is considered linear non-linear
336 if the objective function and/or the constraints are linear non-linear and non-convex
337 if the constraints define a non-convex problem. The existence and uniqueness of the
338 solution can be guaranteed by Kuhn-Tucker conditions [79]. In the present problem,
339 F_{obj} is a non-linear function with the inequality constraints (Eq. (37)) that define a
340 non-convex domain. Although, in this case the existence and uniqueness of the solution
341 is not guaranteed, with a proper selection of initial guesses a feasible and local minimum
342 solution has been found for the problem.

343 By adopting the optimisation approach, the identified parameters for the micropolar
344 model are presented in Table 2 for both armchair and zigzag CNTs;

Table 2. Identified material parameters for armchair and zigzag CNTs as micropolar materials

Parameter	G	l_t	ψ	N	h	α	$\beta + \gamma$	μ	κ	norm(F_{obj})
Unit	GPa	Å	-	-	Å	nN	nN	GPa	GPa	-
Armchair	1177	2.3	1.5	0.15	1.032	-43	129	1152	51	0.0039
Zigzag	1016	3.7	1.49	0.19	1.035	-94	285	979	74	0.0039

345 In addition, Table 3 shows the obtained material parameters considering the couple
346 stress theory.

Table 3. Identified material parameters for armchair and zigzag CNTs as couple stress materials

Parameter	G	l_t	h	norm(F_{obj})
Unit	GPa	Å	Å	-
Armchair	1168	0.6	1.14	0.02
Zigzag	1190	0.9	1.05	0.03

Figure 4. Comparison of apparent shear modulus from micropolar and couple stress models with MD results-the abscissa refers to the mean diameter, d_0

347 Finally, in Table 4, the corresponding shear moduli for the classical Cauchy model
 348 are presented. Note that for Cauchy model, the only unknown parameter is the product
 349 of shear modulus and thickness, Gh , therefore, a freedom in the choice of thickness exist
 350 when considering the Cauchy model. In this regard, without the loss of generality, a
 351 thickness equal to the ones obtained in micropolar case are considered for the sake of
 352 comparison.

Table 4. Identified material parameters for armchair and zigzag CNTs as classical materials

Parameter	G	h	norm(F_{obj})
Unit	GPa	Å	-
Armchair	1330	1.032	0.06
Zigzag	1278	1.035	0.11

353 It is clear from the Tables 2 and 3, that the application of couple stress theory and
 354 Cauchy theory increases the norm of the objective function. For better clarification, in
 355 Fig. 4 a comparison is made between the predicted apparent shear modulus by the
 356 micropolar and couple stress models with those obtained by MD simulation.

357 In addition, for a more general comparison, the prediction of apparent shear modu-
 358 lus by all the three theories considering the same wall thickness are presented in Fig.
 359 5. The occurrence of size effect in the torsional rigidity of armchair and zigzag CNTs is
 360 clearly captured in this figure. If the material could be modeled as a classical Cauchy
 361 material, ($\Omega = 1$), the shear modulus should have been constant for all the simulated
 362 CNTs, while, a decreasing trend is observed in MD simulation results. This decreasing
 363 trend can be predicted by both couple stress and micropolar theories. However, it is
 364 evident from the Fig. 5 that the micropolar theory predicts the MD-simulated torsional
 365 rigidity much more successfully than the couple stress theory. Besides, the effective

Figure 5. Comparison of apparent shear modulus from micropolar, couple stress and Cauchy models with MD results

366 prediction of torsional behaviour by micropolar theory compared to couple stress theory,
 367 suggests the presence of non-symmetric stress and strain measures during the torsional
 368 loading of CNT, which can only be accounted for by micropolar theory. The presence
 369 of non-symmetric stress and strain measures, peculiarity of the micropolar model, may
 370 originate from the difference between the arrangements of carbon hexagonal lattices in
 371 the axial and circumferential directions of CNTs. It also indicates the existence of relative
 372 rotation (the difference between micro and macro rotation) which corresponds to the
 373 skew-symmetric part of stress and strain tensors.

374 In addition, to validate the obtained parameters, the product of $\Omega_h G \times h$ is com-
 375 pared with $G \times h$ in previously reported experimental and numerical results [80,81]. Gh
 376 is also known as surface modulus, however, in the present study $\Omega_h G$ is used instead of
 377 G to define the surface modulus. That is because in an experimental test or a simulation,
 378 the introduced apparent shear modulus is sensed as the rigidity modulus when a torque
 379 is applied on a single CNT (see Eq. (25)). In an experiment conducted by Hall [81],
 380 a value of 410 GPa is reported for G considering a thickness of 3.4 Å for CNTs with
 381 diameters around 9.7 Å. This yields to a surface modulus of 139.4 GPa.nm. This is
 382 quite near to 139.3 GPa.nm value of surface modulus obtained in the present paper for
 383 SWCNT(7,7) with 9.4 Å diameter. Also, by performing MD simulations, Khoei et al.
 384 reported a value of 394 GPa with a thickness of 3.4 Å which results in a value of 134
 385 GPa.nm for the surface modulus of a SWCNT(10,10)[80]. This value is also consistent
 386 with 135.5 GPa.nm for the surface modulus of SWCNT(10,10) in the present paper.

387 In order to show the transferability of the obtained micropolar parameters from the
 388 present approach, one can use the extracted values to predict other mechanical behavior
 389 of CNTs like critical torque. This can be a next step to be performed in a further study.

390 4.1. Equivalent Thickness

391 There is a controversy among researchers for the value of SWCNT's thickness. The
 392 reported values for the effective thickness of SWCNTs have varied from 0.617 Å to 6.9 Å
 393 [64]. Khademolhosseini et al [38] reported a value of 0.85 Å by matching critical torques
 394 obtained by MD-simulations and non-local shell model. Kudin et al. [82] used values of
 395 bending rigidity and in-plane stiffness obtained from ab-initio simulations together with
 396 their classical continuum definitions and reported a value of 0.89 for CNT shell thickness.
 397 One of the most important studies about the wall thickness of the SWCNTs was carried
 398 out by Vodenitcharova and Zhang [78]. Based on the consideration of force equilibrium
 399 and equivalence, they proposed a necessary condition (but not sufficient) for justifying
 400 an effective thickness of SWCNTs that should be smaller than the theoretical diameter
 401 of a carbon atom (~ 1.42 Å). This is known as the Vodenitcharova-Zhang criterion.

402 Their argument is that the cross-section of a nanotube contains only a number of atoms
 403 and that the forces in the nanotube are transmitted through these atoms. However, in a
 404 continuum mechanics-based model the same forces are transmitted through a continuous
 405 wall. Hence, the effective wall thickness cannot be greater than or equal to the theoretical
 406 diameter of a carbon atom, otherwise, the nanotube's equilibrium cannot be maintained.
 407 Based on this criterion, the assumed value of 3.4 \AA , as well as those larger than 1.42 \AA ,
 408 e.g., 6.9 \AA and 1.47 \AA , should be excluded in future investigations.

409 In the present work, the thickness is calculated through the optimisation process. It
 410 is found to be 1.033 \AA and 1.035 \AA , for armchair and zigzag CNTs, respectively. These
 411 values satisfies the Vodenitcharova and Zhang criterion and is near to the values reported
 412 in [82] and [38].

Figure 6. Periodic dimension in the axial direction related to the determined internal length parameter for zigzag and armchair CNTs, “ a ” is the carbon-carbon bond $\sim 1.42 \text{ \AA}$

413 4.2. Internal length parameter

414 The internal length parameter is actually a measure of the internal structure of a material.
 415 It may refer to different physical features; the brick size in a masonry material, the
 416 size of reinforcing particles in a composite and the radius of gyration for a polymeric
 417 material are some of the examples. For nanostructures, the internal length parameter
 418 is considered to be in the order of atomic distances. Focusing on CNTs internal length
 419 parameter, l_t , some researchers used the fixed value of carbon-carbon bond ($\sim 1.42 \text{ \AA}$)
 420 in their non-local models [38]. Khajueenejad and Ghanbari [48] proposed different values
 421 for internal length parameter in the range of 4 to 10 \AA for armchair and zigzag CNTs.
 422 Akbarzadeh and Soltani [49] added another length scale parameter to the modified
 423 couple stress theory named micro-inertia length scale parameter. The original length
 424 parameter varied while they fixed the so-called micro inertia parameter to be in the order
 425 of the lattice size.

426 In the present paper a unique internal length parameter is obtained from the
 427 optimisation procedure, for different diameters in each class of CNTs. This is more
 428 meaningful considering the lattice nature of the structure. The internal length parameter
 429 is determined as 2.3 \AA and 3.7 \AA for armchair and zigzag CNTs, respectively. These
 430 values can be related to the periodic dimension in the axial direction as illustrated in
 431 Fig. 6. Also, from the above discussion, a reasonable prediction is that the value of l_t for
 432 any chiral CNT should fall within the range of internal length of armchair and zigzag
 433 nanotubes as they form the extreme cases of chirality, this can be proved by analyzing a
 434 chiral CNT in a further study.

435 4.3. CNT as solid micropolar cylinder

436 To complete this section, Table 5 presents the obtained material parameters considering
 437 CNT as a solid cylinder and adopting micropolar, couple stress and Cauchy continuum
 438 models with the same procedure previously described.

Figure 7. Comparison of apparent shear modulus from micropolar and couple stress and Cauchy models with MD results-solid cylinder assumption

Table 5. Identified material parameters for armchair and zigzag CNTs as solid cylinders

Parameter	G	l_t	ψ	N	norm(F_{obj})
Unit	GPa	Å	-	-	-
Micropolar					
Armchair	214	5.5	1.4	0.7	0.0022
Zigzag	184	6	1.4	0.7	0.0043
Couple stress					
Armchair	459	2.4	-	-	0.01
Zigzag	418	2.5	-	-	0.012
Cauchy					
Armchair	891	-	-	-	0.78
Zigzag	825	-	-	-	0.78

439 Considering the solid cylinder assumption, the comparison between the predicted
 440 apparent shear modulus by micropolar, couple stress and Cauchy models with those
 441 obtained by MD simulation are presented in Fig. 7.

442 According to Table 5, the smallest objective norm still belongs to the micropolar
 443 model. Besides, Fig. 7, clearly shows that the predicted values by micropolar theory
 444 matches very well with the MD-simulated results.

445 The plot of $\frac{J}{d^2}$ vs. d^2 for armchair and zigzag CNTs is presented in Fig. 8. The trend
 446 of obtained $\frac{J}{d^2}$ suitably obeys the micropolar one proposed by Lake in Fig. 3. Passing a
 447 linear line through the last two data of each plot yields to the value of $G = 312 \text{ GPa}$ and
 448 $l_t = 3.5$ for armchair CNTs and $G = 257 \text{ GPa}$ and $l_t = 3.9$ for zigzag CNTs. Although
 449 the values predicted graphically by the Lake's figure differ from the obtained values
 450 by the optimisation process, they are in the same orders. However, it seems that more
 451 scattered data for CNTs, especially considering larger diameters, are needed to increase
 452 the accuracy of the graphical prediction.

453 5. Conclusion

454 Common practise of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) in nanoscopic field reveals the need
 455 to determine corresponding mechanical properties. Although atomistic simulations
 456 provide accurate and deep information in that aspect, severe computational expenses
 457 are imposed on the problem which limits the size and time scale of the studied atomic
 458 system. Hence, when gross mechanical behaviour of a discrete assembly is looked
 459 for, it is favourable to resort equivalent non-classical continua formulations, which are

Figure 8. Comparison of apparent shear modulus from micropolar and couple stress and Cauchy models with MD results-solid cylinder assumption

460 capable of retaining the memory of internal material organisation while exploiting the
 461 efficiency of continuum analysis. The present paper aims to show the applicability of
 462 micropolar continuum theory, that is endowed with additional kinematic descriptors
 463 and work-conjugated skew-symmetric and couple stress measures, to model size dependent
 464 mechanical behaviour of CNTs, whose underlying lattice structure indicates the
 465 essence of micro-rotations. By comparing the apparent shear modulus of discrete models
 466 obtained from molecular dynamics simulation for moderately short nanotubes and the
 467 ones in continuum micropolar beam model, corresponding material properties as well
 468 as the tube thickness is derived, exploiting a non-linear optimisation procedure. The
 469 tube thickness is determined to be 1.033 Å and 1.035 Å, for armchair and zigzag CNTs,
 470 respectively which satisfies the Vodenitcharova and Zhang criterion and is consistent
 471 with reported values in literature. In addition, a unified internal length parameter is
 472 obtained for different diameters in each class of CNTs which is found to be relevant
 473 with their hexagonal lattice structure. Besides the common assumption of CNTs as
 474 hollow tubes, solid cross-sectional area is also considered as it can be expedient when
 475 dealing with a reinforcement element in composite structure. The predicted torsional
 476 rigidities are further compared with the ones obtained via couple stress and Cauchy
 477 theories. The results clearly depicts the success of micropolar theory as it is perfectly
 478 able to capture trend of discrete model by accounting not only for size effects, but also
 479 for non-symmetries in strain and stress measures in contrast to couple stress theory. In
 480 the present contribution, the torsional behaviour is considered due to a better correspondence
 481 between the boundary conditions of theoretical model and MD simulations, with which all the
 482 mechanical properties are obtained. However, the procedure can be further extended to
 483 different loading conditions with sensible scale-effects. The material parameters predicted
 484 in this study can also be used in different static problems of CNTs. Moreover, the number
 485 of MD simulations can be increased which will inherently improve the precision/accuracy
 486 of the optimisation procedure.

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